

The Implementation of Technology Based Teaching Strategy to Motivating Student's Learning: An Overview

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Abstract: The purpose of teaching has not been understood within the new scenario. Information needn't tend rather it's to be extracted from the learners. Only a few things are new the learners now. They see, hear, read tons from TV, Internet, and therefore the newspaper. The most role of the teacher, therefore, is to assist students organize, create, and share the knowledge they're gathering. Before we see how ICT are often wont to teach, allow us to list the issues during a regular Indian classroom sizable amount of scholars, students with different abilities, lack of space, deficient attention, lack of exhibit facilities, vast syllabus. Can technology help? You'll see a drastic change within the attention and participation of scholars if technology is incorporated into the pedagogies. For that, we first got to change our approach to teaching. We'd like to involve students within the teaching-learning process. Gathering information is feasible through technology. The teacher only has got to facilitate this gathering of data. Young people are very drawn to technology news. Educators must use technology tools in their lectures to stay the eye of young students. Any new technology opens new possibilities for teaching! As an example, the web has opened great possibilities for innovative ways and methods of studying.

Keywords: Technology, Quality Teaching, Motivating Learning Environment, Research Factor, Teaching Strategies, Offline Teaching-Learning.

1. CONCEPT AND MEANING OF TECHNOLOGY BASED TEACHING

Technology has advanced at a speed that man never thought possible ten years ago and it's now spread its tentacles in varied areas, like banking, communication, travel, etc. except for the needs of this text, our interest isn't in IT or Information Technology, but in ICT or Information and Communication Technology. What's the difference? Information and communication technologies is a different set of technological tools and resources wont to correspond, and to make, disseminate, store, and manage information. ICT has been largely related to computer and Internet usage. Nonetheless, technology also includes Television, Radio, LCD Projectors, Audio and Video devices, etc. ICT deals with not only information but communication also. ICT means creating information and sharing it. Computers, mobiles, Internet, radio, TV, and such devices help us do this.

The present generation has quick access to any quite information they need. The thrust, today, is on dissemination instead of accumulation of data and on sharing it. But if we glance at the transactions within the classrooms, it's still the teacher talking and students listening. But this technique of teaching-

learning won't add a modern era. We'd like to shift as of giving information to 'constructing' knowledge. This is often where the scholar becomes a lively learner and teacher a facilitator of learning. This paradigm shift should happen.

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2. VARIOUS WAYS OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING

1. Use of multimedia (computer, LCD projectors, and speakers) within the classroom- The pedagogies depends on the character of the subject. Certain topics are easily adaptable to group discussions, while some got to be explained, some are often debated, while others require lab work. For a subject that needs many pictures, animation, videos, etc., to be shown, multimedia is often utilized in the classroom. PowerPoint is extremely useful in making multimedia presentations on topics of study. Pictures and knowledge on a spread of topics are available on the web, but you'll use your own photos and videos in your PowerPoint lessons. All the knowledge within the textbook needn't be reproduced within the ppt. Students might be given worksheets to reply to base on the ppt because the lesson proceeds. This helps to assimilate information.

Teacher should follow three different phases:

- Initial – to make an ideal environment
- Main development- to expand the subject
- Discussion/assessment - discuss, recap, assess

Multimedia is often used for all three, but mainly within the initial phase. If you're teaching a poem by Mahadevi Verma, an image of the poet, places, events associated with the poem, pictures showing the life-style in Bengal during the poet's lifetime, etc., will help set the stage for you to show further. Malgudi Days are often better understood by today's mall hopping generation if the scene and setting of the story are often created for them on the computer. If the lesson is about Hadappa Mohenjodaro Culture, then short videos can showing then, the Homes, life-style in those times, the social situation that cause the establishment might be shown. Showing children life then will help create the environment and interest required to find out more. How did English communicate with the Indian rulers, traders? If the lesson is about the Animal, then pictures, videos of various sorts of organisms and therefore the environment, they're found in, etc. are often shown very effectively on PPT. If the lesson is about the digestive or the system respiratory then computers are often of great help. An animated video of what happens inside our bodies once we eat or breathe is that the best tool to incite children's curiosity.

2. Use of computers in teaching (without the Internet) - Computers have used for teaching within the computer lab. This is often a really different sort of teaching from use of multimedia within the classroom. During this method, 4 or 5 students are given a computer. The teacher prepares a ppt for a subject and loads it on all the computers. The ppt contains instructions, tasks and questions for college kids to reply to. It's made to encourage discussion among the group members, collate their ideas and share. The subject is presented through related situation.

This can be tailored to suit students of various abilities.

- Students can store and add their word doc for the teacher to ascertain and respond.
- The presentation can end with a discussion about the subject.

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- Try to urge the scholars to use the varied applications on the pc to form their responses more interesting.
- If you're teaching about Trapezium, ask the scholars to draw a trapezium on the pc and colour it.
- If you're teaching about soil ask students to draw the layers of soil on computer and colour them.

3. Use of Internet in teaching - The possibilities of using the web within the classroom is many. The teacher can create a blog to store pictures, lessons, worksheets, assignments, notes associated with a subject. This manner the teacher can discuss the subject anywhere and with many students even outside the classroom. Students also can upload their work on the blog. If you type 'teacher blog' in Google you'll get many sites which will assist you to make a blog of your own. Your students can have their own accounts in your blog. This helps to supplement your teaching by providing more information and a platform for college kids to share their ideas, which isn't always possible during a large class. Shy, introvert, slow students also get an opportunity to participate. You'll give diversified assignments that students can choose between. You'll test the scholars and mark them too. Students get an opportunity to find out and relearn, undergo the subject several times ask questions without being embarrassed. You'll also ask students to urge information from sites associated with the subject.

4. Use of TV, Radio in teaching - The students might be given assignments supported radio, TV programmes on history, geography, science, and environment. This not only creates interest within the students but also enables them to urge more information. This might be shared within the class. It are often planned in such how that much of the syllabus might be covered. The teacher needn't teach all topics within the class. Some might be presented by the scholars and supplemented by the teacher.

3. ADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGY BASED TEACHING

1. Fast Communication Factor - The modern technologies illuminate all geographical boundaries, so students can join various projects all round the world. It's also possible to find out about new cultures and languages without leaving your home! It's sort of a fantasy that has become a reality. Students can exchange files between one another at fantastic speed with no limits on space!

2. Motivating Factor - Young people are very drawn to technology news. Educators must use technology tools in their lectures to stay the eye of young students. Any new technology opens new possibilities for teaching! As an example, the web has opened great possibilities for innovative ways and methods of studying.

3. Cooperative Factor - the chance of cooperative learning made available via ICT encourages dialog between students! They will also study the ideas of collaboration from the web. It makes teachers' jobs easier as they will approach their students with the assistance of recent technologies. Same thing applies to the teachers; they will share knowledge or facts about their students and monitor the general progress during a classroom via technology.

4. Research Factor - it is obvious that with internet and modern technologies, it's become ineffective to form any quite research in libraries alone. The web is an open world to the various sorts of knowledge for college kids. With the vast number of tools hospitable them, the web is impossible to resist! That's why an educator should help students find materials for his or her research papers!

5. Modern Skills Factor - A student can acquire any quite skill with the utilization of technology, for instance, by simply watching self-education videos on YouTube, you'll acquire many new skills. They will also learn new languages using modern technologies without having any teacher around them. Once they know the fundamentals, it's even possible to use their skills right away.

4. DISADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGY BASED TEACHING

1. Privacy Factor - Nobody can avoid the matter of no privacy on the web and tons of criminals use the web to scam people. Therefore, students are highly susceptible to any fraud on the web. That's why teachers should provide lectures to students about the risks on the internet.

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2. Entertainment Factor - It may take ages for college kids to organize for classes with the web. They spend a lot of time on entertainment instead of learning new things, and spend less time on housework. It's therefore necessary to strictly instruct students to understand the difference between time for entertainment and studying.

3. Procrastination Factor - a lot of scholars don't study the themes they have on the internet! Rather than this, they learn tons of things that are unnecessary or maybe harmful to them. That's why an educator should provide guidance on which type of data they have and which they don't.

5. VARIOUS APPROACHES OF TECHNOLOGY BASED TEACHING

1. Technologies are merely tools which will be utilized in a spread of the way. What matters more is how technologies are applied. An equivalent technology is often applied in several ways, even or especially in education. So in judging the worth of a technology, we'd like to seem more closely at the ways during which it's being or might be used. In essence this suggests focusing more on media – which represent the more holistic use of technologies – than on individual tools or technologies themselves, while still recognising that technology is an important component of just about all media.

2. By that specialize in media instead of technologies; we will then include face-to-face teaching as a medium, enabling comparisons with more technology-based media to be made along variety of dimensions or characteristics.

3. Recognising that in education media are usually utilized in combination, the six key building blocks of media are:

- a. Face-to-face teaching
- b. Text
- c. Graphics
- d. Audio (including speech)
- e. Video
- f. Computing (including animation, simulations and virtual reality).

4. Media differ in terms of their formats, symbols systems, and cultural values. These unique features are increasingly mentioned because the affordances of media or technology. Thus different media are often wont to assist learners to find out in several ways and achieve different outcomes, thus also individualising learning more.

5. There are many dimensions along which some technologies are similar et al. are different. By that specialize in these dimensions; we've a basis for analyzing new media and technologies, to ascertain where they 'fit' within the prevailing landscape, and to gauge their potential benefits or limitations for teaching and learning.

6. There are probably other characteristics or dimensions of educational media which may even be identified, but three key characteristics or dimensions are particularly important:

- a. Broadcast vs. communicative
- b. Synchronous (live) vs. asynchronous (recorded)
- c. Single vs. rich media

7. However, the identification of where a specific medium fits along any specific characteristic or dimension will depend in most cases on how that medium is meant. At an equivalent time, there's usually a limit to how far a technology are often forced along one among these dimensions; there's likely to be one , 'natural' position on each dimension, subject to good design, in terms of exploiting the tutorial affordances of the medium.

8. These characteristics or dimensions of media then got to be evaluated against the training goals and outcomes desired, while recognizing that a replacement educational medium or application might enable goals to be achieved that had not been previously considered possible.

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9. Over time, media have attended become more communicative, asynchronous, and 'rich', thus offering teachers and learners more powerful tools for teaching and learning.

10. The web is a particularly powerful medium because through a mixture of tools and media it can encompass all the characteristics and dimensions of education.

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